

New Results on k -prime Labeling

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Abstract. In this paper, we introduce new results on k -prime labeling. First, we discuss the k -prime labeling of cycles C_n for some values of k and n . Also we give the k -prime labeling of combs $P_n \odot K_1$ and some case of the crown $C_n \odot K_1$. Second, we show that all wheels W_{2n+1} are not k -prime for every positive integers k and n while W_{2n} ($n \geq 2$) is not k -prime for every even positive integers k . Finally, we give the k -prime labeling of the helm H_n ($n \geq 3$) for $2 \leq k \leq 11$ and we show that if $k + 2(n - 1)$ and $k + 2n$ are twin primes where $n \geq 3$ and $k \geq 1$, then H_n is k -prime.

Introduction

The notion of prime labeling originated with Entringer and was introduced in a paper by Tout et al. [12]. A graph G with vertex set $V(G)$ is said to have a prime labeling if there exist a bijection $f : V(G) \rightarrow \{1, 2, \dots, |V(G)|\}$ such that for each edge $xy \in E(G)$, $f(x)$ and $f(y)$ are relatively prime. A graph that admits a prime labeling is called a *prime graph*. Around 1980 Entringer conjectured, that all trees are prime. Paths, stars, caterpillar, complete binary trees, spiders have prime labeling (see [4]). In 1999, Seoud and Youssef [10] conjectured that all unicyclic graphs are prime. In 2011, Vaidya and Prajapati [13] gave a variation of the definition of prime labeling. They call a graph G of order n is k -prime for some positive integer k if its vertices can labeled bijectively by the labels $k, k + 1, \dots, k + n - 1$ such that adjacent vertices receive relatively prime labels. For known results on the prime labeling and its variations see [1-14]. The reference [4] surveyed the known results to all variations of graph labelings appearing in this paper. In this paper we give new results on k -prime labeling. All graphs in this chapter are simple, finite, and undirected.

2. k -prime labeling of cycles and related graphs

In this section we investigate the k -prime labeling of cycles, combs and crowns for some positive integer values k . We well denoted to the vertices of the path or the cycle by

u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n and the pendant edges of the comb or the crown by v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n . However, we have the following necessary condition for the graph to be k -prime.

Lemma 2.1 If G is a k -prime graph of order n with a k -prime labeling function f and let $E_2 = \{k \leq t \leq k + n - 1 : t \text{ is even}\}$, then $\beta(G) \geq |E_2|$, where

$$|E_2| = \begin{cases} \left\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \right\rfloor & \text{if } k \text{ is odd} \\ \left\lceil \frac{n}{2} \right\rceil & \text{if } k \text{ is even} \end{cases}$$

Proof Since we have $|E_2|$ even vertex labels, then we must have $\beta(G) \geq |E_2|$. ■

Note that if n is even in the above lemma, then we have $|E_2| = \frac{n}{2}$ for every value of k . The following result shows that if C_n is k -prime then either n is even or k is odd.

Corollary 2.2 C_{2n+1} is not k -prime for all even positive integer k .

Proof Comes directly from Lemma 3.1.1, since $\beta(C_{2n+1}) = n < |E_2| = n + 1$. ■

From the above result we may deal with the k -prime labeling of cycles when n is odd and k is odd or when k is even and for every k .

Theorem 2.3 C_{2^n+1} is k -prime if and only if k is odd.

Proof Necessity comes from Corollary 3.1.2. For sufficiency, label the vertices of the cycle consecutively by the labels $k, k + 1, \dots, k + 2^n$ where k is the label of u_1 and $k + 2^n$ is the label of u_{2^n+1} . Since $(k, k + 2^n) = (k, 2^n) = 1$, as k is odd. Thus C_{2^n+1} is k -prime. ■

Theorem 2.4 C_4 is k -prime if and only if $k \not\equiv 0 \pmod{3}$.

Proof Necessity, let $k \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$, the set of vertex labels is: $\{k, k + 1, k + 2, k + 3\}$ so, we put the labels k and $k + 3$ on non adjacent vertices of C_4 . We check the other two nonadjacent vertices: We note one of the labels of the set $\{k, k + 3\}$ is odd and one is even and as $k, k + 1$ are two consecutive integers. So, none of the remaining vertices cannot assign the even label from the set $\{k + 1, k + 2\}$. Hence C_4 is not k -prime. For sufficiency, let

$k \not\equiv 0 \pmod{3}$. Define $f: V(C_4) \rightarrow \{k, k + 1, k + 2, k + 3\}$ as follow:

$$f(u_i) = k - 1 + i, \quad 1 \leq i \leq 4$$

We have to show that the labeling works:

Since, $(k, k + 3) = (k, 3) = 1$ since $k \not\equiv 0 \pmod{3}$. ■

Theorem 2.5 The comb $P_n \odot K_1$ is k -prime for every positive integer k .

Proof Define $f : V(P_n \odot K_1) \rightarrow \{k, k + 1, \dots, k + 2n - 1\}$ as in the following two cases according to parity of k .

Case 1. k is even:

$$\begin{aligned} f(u_i) &= k + 2i - 1, & 1 \leq i \leq n \\ f(v_j) &= k + 2(j - 1), & 1 \leq j \leq n. \end{aligned}$$

Case 2. k is odd:

$$\begin{aligned} f(u_i) &= k + 2(i - 1), & 1 \leq i \leq n \\ f(v_j) &= k + 2j - 1, & 1 \leq j \leq n. \end{aligned}$$

■

Theorem 2.6 $C_n \odot K_1$ is 2^i -prime for all $n \geq 3$ and $i \geq 1$.

Proof Put $k = 2^i$. Define $f : V(C_n \odot K_1) \rightarrow \{k, k + 1, \dots, k + 2n - 1\}$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} f(u_1) &= k \\ f(u_i) &= k + 2i - 3, & 2 \leq i \leq n \\ f(v_1) &= k + 2n - 1 \\ f(v_j) &= k + 2(j - 1), & 2 \leq j \leq n. \end{aligned}$$

■

The following result enlarge the class of crowns that have k -prime labeling.

Theorem 2.7 If p is an odd prime, then $C_n \odot K_1$ is p^i -prime for all $i \geq 1$ and $n \not\equiv 1 \pmod{p}$.

Proof Let $f : V(C_n \odot K_1) \rightarrow \{p^i, \dots, 2n + p^i - 1\}$. We have two cases:

Case 1: $n \not\equiv 1 \pmod{p}$

Define f as follow:

$$\begin{aligned} f(u_i) &= 2i + (p^i - 2), & 1 \leq i \leq n \\ f(v_j) &= 2j + (p^i - 1), & 1 \leq j \leq n. \end{aligned}$$

Case 2: $n \equiv 1 \pmod{p}$

Define f as follow:

$$f(u_i) = 2i + (p^i - 2), \quad 1 \leq i \leq n - 2$$

$$f(u_n) = 2n + (p^i - 4)$$

$$f(u_{n-1}) = 2n + (p^i - 2)$$

$$f(v_j) = 2j + (p^i - 1), \quad 1 \leq j \leq n - 2$$

$$f(v_n) = 2n + (p^i - 3).$$

$$f(v_{n-1}) = 2n + (p^i - 1). \quad \blacksquare$$

We investigate the k -prime labeling of wheels W_n for some value of n and for fixed value integer k . In the wheels $W_n = C_n + K_1$, the vertex corresponding to K_1 is called the *apex vertex* and is denoted by u_0 , while the vertices corresponding to cycle C_n are called the *rim vertices* and are denoted by u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n where u_i is adjacent to u_0 for each $1 \leq i \leq n$. However we have the following results.

Lemma 2.8 W_{2n+1} is not k -prime for all $k \geq 1$ and $n \geq 1$.

Proof Comes straightforward from Lemma 2.1, since the order of the wheel W_{2n+1} is even and

$\beta(W_{2n+1}) = n < |E_2| = \frac{2n+2}{2} = n+1$ for any k , where E_2 is the set of even vertex labels, then W_{2n+1} is not k -prime. \blacksquare

Lemma 2.9 W_{2n} is not k -prime for all $n \geq 2$ and for every even positive integer k .

Proof Comes straightforward from Lemma 2.1, since k is even and

$\beta(W_{2n}) = n < |E_2| = \left\lceil \frac{2n+1}{2} \right\rceil = n+1$, where E_2 is the set of even vertex labels, W_{2n} is not k -prime. \blacksquare

Theorem 2.10 W_n is k -prime if and only if $k \equiv 1 \pmod{6}$.

Proof Necessity, we have two cases

Case 1: $k \equiv 0, 2 \text{ or } 4 \pmod{6}$

By Lemma 2.2, W_n is k -prime.

Case 2: $k \equiv 3 \text{ or } 5 \pmod{6}$

Suppose W_n is k -prime, then we must label two independent rim vertices of the wheel by the even labels $k+1$ and $k+3$. Then we can not find a vertex of the wheel to put the vertex

label k in case $k \equiv 3 \pmod{6}$ or to put the vertex label $k + 5$ in case $k \equiv 5 \pmod{6}$, a contradiction and hence the wheel is not k -prime in this case.

For sufficiency, let $k \equiv 1 \pmod{6}$, we define a function $f: V(W_n) \rightarrow \{k, k + 1, \dots, k + 4\}$ as follow:

$$f(u_0) = k$$

$$f(u_i) = k + i, \quad 1 \leq i \leq 4$$

We have to show that the labeling works:

For $1 \leq i \leq 4$,

- $(f(u_0), f(u_i)) = (k, k + i) = (k, i) = (6t + 1, i) = 1$.
 - $(f(u_1), f(u_4)) = (k + 1, k + 4) = (k + 1, 3) = 1$.
- as $k \equiv 1 \pmod{6}$. ■

3. k -prime labeling of helms

In this section we investigate the k -prime labeling of helms for some values of k . The helm H_n is the graph obtained from the wheel $W_n = C_n + K_1$ ($n \geq 3$) by attaching a pendant edge at every vertex of the n -cycle. We shall denote to the centre vertex of the helm by u_0 , the vertices of the n -cycle by u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n and the pendant edges by v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n where u_i is adjacent to v_i for each $1 \leq i \leq n$. Although the wheel W_{2n+1} is not $2k$ -prime for all positive integer k , we did not find yet positive integers $k \geq 2$ and $n \geq 3$ for which a helm H_n is not k -prime and we conjecture that the helm H_n is k -prime for every positive integer k . Seoud and Youssef [10] showed that H_n is prime for all $n \geq 3$. However, we have the following results.

Theorem 3.1 H_n is 2-prime for all $n \geq 3$.

Proof Let $f: V(H_n) \rightarrow \{2, 3, \dots, 2n + 2\}$ be a function. We have two cases:

Case 1: $n \not\equiv 1 \pmod{3}$

Define f as follows:

$$f(u_0) = 2$$

$$f(u_i) = 2i + 1, \quad 1 \leq i \leq n$$

$$f(v_j) = 2j + 2, \quad 1 \leq j \leq n$$

Case 2 : $n \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$

Define f as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 f(u_0) &= 2 \\
 f(u_i) &= 2i + 1, 1 \leq i \leq n - 2 \\
 f(u_n) &= 2n - 1 \\
 f(u_{n-1}) &= 2n + 1 \\
 f(v_i) &= 2i + 2, 1 \leq i \leq n
 \end{aligned}$$

Clearly f is injective function in both cases. It can be easily verified that f is a 2-prime labeling of H_n . ■

Theorem 3.2 H_n is 3-prime for all $n \geq 3$.

Proof Let $f: V(H_n) \rightarrow \{3, 4, \dots, 2n + 3\}$ be a function. We have two cases:

Case 1 : $n \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$

In this case define as follow:

$$\begin{aligned}
 f(u_0) &= 4 \\
 f(u_i) &= 2i + 1, 1 \leq i \leq n \\
 f(v_j) &= 2j + 2, 2 \leq j \leq n - 1 \\
 f(v_1) &= 2n + 2, \quad f(v_n) = 2n + 3
 \end{aligned}$$

We have to show that the labeling works:

- $(f(u_i), f(u_0)) = (2i + 1, 4) = 1$ for each $1 \leq i \leq n$
- $(f(u_i), f(v_i)) = (2i + 1, 2i + 2) = (2i + 1, 1) = 1, 2 \leq i \leq n - 1$
- $(f(u_1), f(v_1)) = (3, 2n + 2) = (3, (n + 1)) = 1$
- $(f(u_n), f(v_n)) = (2n + 1, 2n + 3) = 1$

Case 2 : $n \not\equiv 0 \pmod{3}$

Define f as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 f(u_0) &= 4 \\
 f(u_i) &= 2i + 1, 1 \leq i \leq n \\
 f(v_j) &= 2j + 2, 2 \leq j \leq 2 \\
 f(v_1) &= 2n + 3
 \end{aligned}$$

Again, this labeling is works since moreover:

- $(f(v_1), f(u_1)) = (3, 2n + 3) = (3, 2n) = (3, n) = 1$

as $n \not\equiv 0 \pmod{3}$. ■

Theorem 3.3 H_n is 4-prime for all $n \geq 3$.

Proof We have two cases :

Case 1: $n \not\equiv 1(mod5)$

Define a function $f : V(H_n) \rightarrow \{4, 5, \dots, 2n + 4\}$ as follows:

$$f(u_0) = 4$$

$$f(u_i) = 2i + 3, 1 \leq i \leq n$$

$$f(v_j) = 2j + 4, 1 \leq j \leq n.$$

Clearly f is injective function. We show that all adjacent vertices receive relatively prime labels:

- $(f(u_0), f(u_i)) = (4, 2i + 3) = 1$
- $(f(u_i), f(v_i)) = (2i + 3, 2i + 4) = 1$
- $(f(u_i), f(u_{i+1})) = (2i + 3, 2i + 5) = (2i + 3, 2) = 1, 1 \leq i \leq n - 1$
- $(f(u_1), f(u_n)) = (5, 2n + 3) = (5, 2n - 2) = (5, n - 1) = 1$

Case 2: $n \equiv 1(mod5)$

Define a function $f : V(H_n) \rightarrow \{4, 5, \dots, 2n + 4\}$ as follows:

$$f(u_0) = 4$$

$$f(u_i) = 2i + 3, 1 \leq i \leq n - 2$$

$$f(u_{n-1}) = 2n + 3$$

$$f(u_n) = 2n + 1$$

$$f(v_i) = 2i + 4, 1 \leq i \leq n.$$

Clearly f is injective function. Again, it is straightforward to verify that all adjacent vertices receive relatively prime labels. ■

Theorem 3.4 H_n is 5-prime for all $n \geq 3$.

Proof We have three cases :

Case 1: $n \equiv 0(mod5)$

Define $f: V(H_n) \rightarrow \{5, 6, \dots, 2n + 5\}$ as follow:

$$f(u_0) = 8$$

$$f(u_i) = 2i + 5, 1 \leq i \leq n - 2$$

$$f(u_n) = 2n + 3$$

$$f(u_{n-1}) = 2n + 5$$

$$f(v_j) = 2j + 6, 2 \leq j \leq n - 1$$

$$f(v_1) = 6$$

$$f(v_n) = 5$$

We have to show that the labeling works:

- As $f(u_i)$ is odd for each $1 \leq i \leq n$, then $(f(u_i), f(u_0)) = (f(u_i), 8) = 1$.
- $(f(u_i), f(u_{i+1})) = 1, 1 \leq i \leq n - 1$.
- $(f(u_n), f(v_n)) = (2n + 3, 5) = (5, n - 1) = 1$

Case 2: $n \equiv 1(mod5)$

$$f(u_0) = 8$$

$$f(u_i) = 2i + 3, 1 \leq i \leq n - 2$$

$$f(u_{n-1}) = 2n + 3$$

$$f(u_n) = 2n + 1$$

$$f(v_1) = 2n + 4$$

$$f(v_2) = 6$$

$$f(v_j) = 2j + 4, 3 \leq j \leq n - 1$$

$$f(v_n) = 2n + 5$$

We have to show that the labeling works:

- As in case 1, $(f(u_i), f(u_0)) = 1, 1 \leq i \leq n$.
- $(f(u_1), f(u_n)) = (5, 2n + 1) = (5, 2n - 4) = (5, n - 2) = 1$.
- $(f(u_1), f(v_1)) = (5, 2n + 4) = (5, 2n - 1) = 1$.

Case3: $n \not\equiv 0$ and $1(mod5)$

$$f(u_0) = 8$$

$$f(u_i) = 2i + 3, 1 \leq i \leq n$$

$$f(v_j) = 2j + 4, 3 \leq j \leq n$$

$$f(v_2) = 5$$

$$f(v_1) = 2n + 5$$

We must show that the labeling works:

- $(f(u_1), f(u_n)) = (5, 2n + 3) = (5, 2n - 2) = (5, n - 1) = 1, as n \not\equiv 1(mod5)$.
- $(f(u_1), f(v_1)) = (5, 2n + 5) = (5, n) = 1, as n \not\equiv 0(mod5)$. ■

Theorem 3.5 H_n is 6-prime for all $n \geq 3$.

Proof We have two cases:

Case 1: $n \equiv 1(mod7)$

Define $f: V(H_n) \rightarrow \{6,7, \dots, 2n + 6\}$ as follow:

$$\begin{aligned} f(u_0) &= 8 \\ f(u_i) &= 2i + 5, \quad 1 \leq i \leq n - 2 \\ f(u_n) &= 2n + 3 \\ f(u_{n-1}) &= 2n + 5 \\ f(v_j) &= 2j + 6, \quad 2 \leq j \leq n \\ f(v_1) &= 6. \end{aligned}$$

Case 2: $n \not\equiv 1(mod7)$

$$\begin{aligned} f(u_0) &= 8 \\ f(u_i) &= 2i + 5, \quad 1 \leq i \leq n \\ f(v_1) &= 6 \\ f(v_j) &= 2j + 6, \quad 2 \leq j \leq n. \quad \blacksquare \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 3.6 H_n is 7-prime for all $n \geq 3$.

Proof We have three cases:

Case 1: $n \equiv 1(mod7)$

Define $f: V(H_n) \rightarrow \{7,8, \dots, 2n + 7\}$ as follow:

$$\begin{aligned} f(u_0) &= 8 \\ f(u_i) &= 2i + 5, \quad 1 \leq i \leq n - 2 \\ f(u_n) &= 2n + 3 \\ f(u_{n-1}) &= 2n + 5 \\ f(v_j) &= 2j + 6, \quad 2 \leq j \leq n - 1 \\ f(v_1) &= 2n + 6 \\ f(v_n) &= 2n + 7 \end{aligned}$$

Case 2: $n \equiv 0(mod7)$

$$\begin{aligned} f(u_0) &= 8 \\ f(u_i) &= 2i + 5, \quad 1 \leq i \leq n \\ f(v_1) &= 2n + 6 \\ f(v_j) &= 2j + 6, \quad 2 \leq j \leq n - 1 \\ f(v_n) &= 2n + 7 \end{aligned}$$

Case 3: $n \not\equiv 0, 1 \pmod{7}$

$$\begin{aligned} f(u_0) &= 8 \\ f(u_i) &= 2i + 5, 1 \leq i \leq n \\ f(v_j) &= 2j + 6, 2 \leq j \leq n \\ f(v_1) &= 2n + 7. \blacksquare \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 3.7 H_n is 8-prime for all $n \geq 3$.

Proof We have two cases:

Case 1: $n \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$

Define $f: V(H_n) \rightarrow \{8, 9, \dots, 2n + 8\}$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} f(u_0) &= 8 \\ f(u_i) &= 2i + 7, 1 \leq i \leq n - 2 \\ f(u_n) &= 2n + 5 \\ f(u_{n-1}) &= 2n + 7 \\ f(v_j) &= 2j + 8 \end{aligned}$$

Case 2: $n \not\equiv 1 \pmod{3}$

$$\begin{aligned} f(u_0) &= 8 \\ f(u_i) &= 2i + 7, 1 \leq i \leq n \\ f(v_j) &= 2j + 8 \blacksquare \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 3.8 H_n is 9-prime for all $n \geq 3$.

Proof We have three cases:

Case 1: $n \equiv 0 \pmod{3}$

a) If $n > 3$:

Define $f: V(H_n) \rightarrow \{9, 10, \dots, 2n + 9\}$ as follow:

$$\begin{aligned} f(u_0) &= 16 \\ f(u_i) &= 2i + 7, 1 \leq i \leq n \\ f(v_1) &= 2n + 8 \\ f(v_j) &= 2j + 6, 2 \leq j \leq 4 \\ f(v_j) &= 2j + 8, 5 \leq i \leq n - 1 \\ f(v_n) &= 2n + 9 \end{aligned}$$

This labeling is work since:

- $(9, 2n + 8) = (9, n + 4) = 1$.

b) If $n = 3$:

Define $f : V(H_3) \rightarrow \{9, 10, \dots, 15\}$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & f(u_0) = 13 \\ \text{c) } & f(u_1) = 9, \quad f(u_2) = 11, \quad f(u_3) = 14 \\ & f(v_1) = 10, \quad f(u_2) = 12, \quad f(u_3) = 15. \end{aligned}$$

Case 2: $n \equiv 2 \pmod{3}$

The same as in Case 1(a) except for $f(v_1), f(v_n)$.

Define $g : V(H_n) \rightarrow \{9, 10, \dots, 2n + 9\}$ as follow:

$$\begin{aligned} g(v) &= f(v), \quad \forall v \in V(H_n) : v \neq v_1, v_n. \\ g(v_1) &= 2n + 9 \\ g(v_n) &= 2n + 8 \end{aligned}$$

Case 3: $n \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$

$$\begin{aligned} f(u_0) &= 16 \\ f(u_i) &= 2i + 7, \quad 1 \leq i \leq n - 2 \\ f(u_{n-1}) &= 2n + 7 \\ f(u_n) &= 2n + 5 \\ f(v_1) &= 2n + 9 \\ f(v_j) &= 2j + 6, \quad 2 \leq j \leq 4 \\ f(v_j) &= 2j + 8, \quad 5 \leq j \leq n \end{aligned}$$

This labeling is work since:

- $(9, 2n+9) = (9, 2n) = (9, n) = 1$, as $n \equiv 1 \pmod{3}$.
- $(9, 2n+5) = (9, 2n-4) = (9, n-2) = 1$
- $(2n+5, 2n+8) = (2n+5, 3) = 1$. ■

Theorem 3.9 H_n is 10-prime for all $n \geq 3$.

Proof We have two cases:

Case 1: $n \not\equiv 1(\text{mod } 11)$

Define $f : V(H_n) \rightarrow \{10, 11, \dots, 2n + 10\}$ as follow:

$$f(u_0) = 16$$

$$f(u_i) = 2i + 9, \quad 1 \leq i \leq n$$

$$f(v_j) = 2j + 8, \quad 1 \leq j \leq 3$$

$$f(v_j) = 2j + 10, \quad 4 \leq j \leq n$$

This labeling is work since:

- $(f(u_1), f(u_n)) = (11, 2n + 9) = (11, 2n - 2) = (11, n - 1) = 1.$
- $(f(u_i), f(v_i)) = (2i + 9, 2i + 8) = 1, \quad 1 \leq j \leq 3.$
- $(f(u_i), f(v_j)) = (2i + 9, 2i + 10) = 1, \quad 4 \leq i \leq n.$

Case 2: $n \equiv 1(\text{mod } 11)$

$$f(u_0) = 16$$

$$f(u_i) = \begin{cases} 2i + 9, & 1 \leq i \leq n - 2 \\ 2n + 9, & i = n - 1 \\ 2n + 7, & i = n \end{cases}$$

$$f(v_j) = \begin{cases} 2j + 8, & 1 \leq j \leq 3 \\ 2j + 10, & 4 \leq j \leq n - 2 \\ 2n + 10, & j = n - 1 \\ 2n + 8, & j = n \end{cases}$$

This labeling is work since:

- $(f(u_1), f(u_n)) = (11, 2n + 7) = (11, 2n - 4) = (11, n - 2) = 1$

$$\bullet (f(u_i), f(v_i)) = \begin{cases} (2i + 9, 2i + 8) = 1, & 1 \leq i \leq 3 \\ (2i + 9, 2i + 10) = 1, & 4 \leq i \leq n - 2 \\ (2n + 9, 2n + 10) = 1, & i = n - 1 \\ (2n + 7, 2n + 8) = 1, & i = n \end{cases}$$

- $(f(u_n), f(u_{n-1})) = (2n + 7, 2n + 9) = (2n + 7, 2) = 1.$
- $(f(u_{n-2}), f(u_{n-1})) = (2n + 5, 2n + 9) = (2n + 5, 4) = 1. \blacksquare$

Theorem 3.10 H_n is 11-prime for all $n \geq 3$.

Proof We have three cases :

Case 1: $n \equiv 0(\text{mod}11)$

Define $f: V(H_n) \rightarrow \{11, 12, \dots, 2n + 11\}$ as follow:

$$\begin{aligned} f(u_0) &= 16 \\ f(u_i) &= 2i + 9, \quad 1 \leq i \leq n \\ f(v_j) &= 2j + 8, \quad j = 2, 3 \\ f(v_j) &= 2j + 10, \quad 4 \leq j \leq n - 1 \\ f(v_1) &= 2n + 10 \\ f(v_n) &= 2n + 11 \end{aligned}$$

This labeling is work since:

- $(f(u_1), f(u_n)) = (11, 2n + 9) = (11, 2n - 2) = (11, n - 1) = 1$
- $(f(u_1), f(v_1)) = (11, 2n + 10) = (11, 2n - 1) = 1$

Case 2: $n \equiv 1(\text{mod}11)$

$$\begin{aligned} f(u_0) &= 16 \\ f(u_i) &= 2i + 9, \quad 1 \leq i \leq n - 1 \\ f(u_n) &= 2n + 11 \\ f(v_j) &= 2j + 8, \quad j = 2, 3 \\ f(v_j) &= 2j + 10, \quad 4 \leq j \leq n - 1 \\ f(v_1) &= 2n + 10 \\ f(v_n) &= 2n + 9 \end{aligned}$$

This labeling is work since:

- $(f(u_1), f(u_n)) = (11, 2n + 11) = (11, 2n) = (11, n) = 1$
- $(f(u_1), f(v_1)) = (11, 2n + 10) = (11, 2n - 1) = 1$
- **Case 3:** $n \not\equiv 0, 1(\text{mod}11)$

$$f(u_0) = 16$$

$$f(u_i) = 2i + 9, \quad 1 \leq i \leq n$$

$$f(v_j) = 2j + 8, \quad j = 2, 3$$

$$f(v_j) = 2j + 10, \quad 4 \leq j \leq n$$

$$f(v_1) = 2n + 11$$

This labeling is work since:

- $(f(u_1), f(u_n)) = (11, 2n + 9) = (11, 2n - 2) = (11, n - 1) = 1$, as $n \not\equiv 1 \pmod{11}$.
- $(f(u_1), f(v_1)) = (11, 2n + 11) = (11, n) = 1$, as $n \not\equiv 0 \pmod{11}$.

Theorem 3.11 If $k + 2(n - 1)$ and $k + 2n$ are twin primes where $n \geq 3$ and $k \geq 1$, then H_n is k -prime.

Proof Clearly, k must be an odd integer, define

$f : V(H_n) \rightarrow \{k, k + 1, \dots, k + 2n\}$ as follows:

$$f(u_i) = k + 2(i - 1), \quad 1 \leq i \leq n$$

$$f(u_0) = k + 2n$$

$$f(v_j) = k + 2(j - 1) + 1 = k + 2j - 1, \quad 1 \leq j \leq n$$

$$|f(u_i) - f(v_i)| = 1 \Rightarrow (f(u_i), f(v_i)) = 1. \quad \blacksquare$$

Our previous results about the k -prime labeling of the helms for $2 \leq k \leq 11$ motivated us to arise the following conjecture.

Conjecture All helms are k -prime for every positive integer k .

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